

Supplementary Information

Coupling light into a guided Bloch surface wave using an inversely designed nanophotonic cavity

Zongyuan Tang,^{1,2} Tian-Long Guo,³ Yannick Augenstein,^{4,5} Adriano Troia,⁶ Yanjun Liu,² Matthieu Roussey,³ Carsten Rockstuhl,^{4,7} and Emiliano Descrovi¹

¹Dept. of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, 10129 Torino, Italy

²Dept. of Electronic and Electrical Engineering, Southern University of Science and Technology, 518055 Shenzhen, China

³Center for Photonics Sciences, University of Eastern Finland, P.O. Box 111, FI-80101 Joensuu, Finland

⁴Institute of Theoretical Solid State Physics, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

⁵Flexcompute Inc, Belmont, MA, USA

⁶Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRiM), 10135 Torino, Italy

⁷Institute of Nanotechnology, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

Corresponding Authors

Zongyuan Tang: zongyuan.tang@polito.it

Tian-Long Guo: tianlong.guo@uef.fi

Fabrication methods

The 1DPC deposition was performed via plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition (PE-ALD, TFS-200, Beneq, Finland) on a glass coverslip (Corning, refractive index $n_s=1.527$ at $\lambda_0=650$ nm, which had been pre-treated with a 2-minute O_2 plasma. Specifically, TiO_2 , SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 layers were deposited using $TiCl_4$, bis(ethylmethylamino)silane (BEMAS), and trimethylaluminium (TMA) as the respective precursors, while O_2 served as a common oxidizing precursor for all three materials. The nitrogen remote plasma power was maintained at 100 W for all processes, with a deposition temperature set at 150° C.

The cavity and waveguide pattern have been fabricated according to the following procedure. The 1DPC was initially coated with a 30 nm Cr layer (Q300T T Plus, Quorum, UK), then a layer of diluted negative resist (AZ nLof 2070, MicroChemicals, Ulm, Germany) was spin-coated (Laurell WS-650MZ-8NPPB, Lansdale, PA, USA) at 4000 rpm for 60 s. The substrate was subsequently subjected to a 1-minute soft-bake on a 110° C hot plate. The structure was written into the resist layer using electron beam lithography (EBL, Vistec EBPG5000+HR, Dortmund, Germany). Acceleration voltage was set to 100 kV, with an exposure dose of $65 \mu C/cm^2$. Post-exposure, the sample underwent a hard-bake at 110° C for another minute. The pattern development was carried out in AR 300-47 (AllResist, Strausberg, Germany) for 90 s, followed by a 60 s stop in deionized (DI) water, and then rinsing with DI water.

The developed pattern was transferred onto the top SiO_2 layer by initially etching the Cr mask using inductively coupled plasma-reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE) in a PlasmaPro 100 Cobra system (Oxford Instruments). During the etching process, Cl_2 and O_2 gases flowed at rates of 54 and 4 sccm, respectively. The chamber pressure was maintained at 15 mTorr, with RIE and ICP power settings of 10 W and 1200 W, respectively. The etching duration was 45 s, followed by removing polymer residues with an additional 2-minute O_2 plasma treatment.

Finally, using the Cr mask, the pattern was transferred onto SiO_2 employing the ICP-RIE Plasmalab 80Plus system (Oxford Instruments). Active gases CHF_3 and Ar were flowed at rates of 10 and 15 sccm, respectively. The chamber pressure was maintained at 9 mTorr, with RIE and ICP power settings of 30 W and 600 W, respectively. The etching time was 52 s, 2 s of over-etching, to make sure the top SiO_2 layer was fully removed. The etching process was stopped by the thin Al_2O_3 layer underneath. The Cr mask was removed using the aforementioned Cr etching recipe.

Optimization Method

We employed a topology optimization approach for computational feasibility to design the cavity structures that efficiently extract light emitted from a dipole-like source into a waveguide integrated into a Bloch Surface Wave (BSW) platform. The details of the optimization method have been already described in our prior work [SI_1], and we repeat the most important aspects here only for convenience.

Generally, due to the impracticality of optimizing 3D large-scale systems using full wave optimization, the problem was simplified in the optimization to a two-dimensional one using an effective index method. Here, the spatial distribution of a refractive index distribution is optimized. The values the refractive index may attain are derived from the propagation constants of the fundamental BSW sustained in the considered layer stack with or without the last functional layer. The method is suitable for low refractive index contrast systems and has been validated in previous BSW studies [SI_2]. We stress that the final functionality of the devices, as presented in the main manuscript, has been evaluated using full-wave 3D simulation. Only the optimization was done in this 2D simplified setting.

The considered system features a dipole source aligned along the x-axis. The source emits light with a Gaussian spectrum centered at a wavelength of λ_0 . This source is placed at the center of a spacer region within a circular design area with a radius of $5.7 \mu\text{m}$. The goal is to maximize the power coupled into the fundamental forward-propagating TM-polarized mode of a waveguide attached to the design area following. The entire setup is best seen in Fig. 1 (a) of the main manuscript. In the topology optimization, two full-wave simulations are performed, the forward simulation and the adjoint one, to calculate the gradient of an objective function with respect to every degree of freedom. Once the gradients are known, a gradient-descent approach is pursued to iterate the degrees of freedom towards a configuration that maximizes the objective function.

In topology optimization, the degrees of freedom are represented by a design variable $\rho \in [0,1]$ distribution, a filter-and-project method is applied to translate the design variable to an actual material distribution. The method consists of a sequence of steps:

1. Filtering: A Gaussian low-pass filter imposes a minimum feature size of 50 nm, smoothing out high-frequency variations in the design variables.
2. Projection: A soft-thresholding function promotes binarization of the design variables so that it can be used to represent the two possible values the index may attain. The soft-thresholding function works as

$$\hat{\rho} = \frac{\tanh(\beta/2) + \tanh(\beta(\rho - 0.5))}{2 \tanh(\beta/2)}$$

The parameter β controls the steepness of the thresholding curve and is incrementally increased during optimization to refine binarization.

3. Gray Indicator Constraint: Furthermore, to prevent the design from reverting to intermediate (gray) values, the grayness is quantified and constrained:

$$c_g(\hat{\rho}) = \sum_{i=1}^n 4\hat{\rho}_i(1 - \hat{\rho}_i) \leq \gamma$$

The threshold γ is set based on the design after each β increment.

4. Geometrical Masking: Finally, a circular mask is applied to enforce the circular geometry of the device.

The projected design variables are mapped to refractive indices to create the device geometry for simulation. Electromagnetic simulations are made using Meep (version 1.23.0) with MPI parallelization at a spatial resolution of 50 pixels per micrometer.

The sensitivities required for gradient-based optimization are computed in two steps. First, the objective function sensitivities are calculated using Meep's adjoint module, providing derivatives of F with respect to the electromagnetic fields. Then the parametrization sensitivities are obtained via autograd, yielding derivatives of $\hat{\rho}$ with respect to ρ .

Taking all these aspects together, the optimization problem is formulated as:

Maximize: $F = |\alpha_0|^2$

Subject to: $\alpha_0 = \int [\widetilde{E}^*(r) \times \widetilde{H}_0(r) + \widetilde{E}_0(r) \times \widetilde{H}^*(r)] \cdot \hat{n} \, dA$

$$c_g(\hat{\rho}) \leq \gamma$$

$$0 \leq \rho \leq 1$$

where \widetilde{E} and \widetilde{H} are the Fourier-transformed fields at the target wavelength λ_0 as obtained within meep, and \widetilde{E}_0 and \widetilde{H}_0 are the fields of the fundamental mode of the waveguide into which we wish to couple obtained from MPB [56].

For the gradient-based optimization, the Method of Moving Asymptotes implemented in the nlopt library (version 2.7.1) is used to solve the constrained nonlinear optimization problem.

For more details and an extensive discussion of the impact of different parameters in the optimization, we refer to our prior work [SI_1].

Supplementary Figure S1

Figure S1. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images of the fabricated structure. Overall structure (left), details of the cavity center (right).

Supplementary Figure S2

Figure S2. Absolute value of the electric field along a transverse line across the waveguide at a fixed value of y and z (i.e. at $h_{\text{wg}}/2$ below the top surface). We see that the x -component of the electric field is discontinuous (the x -component of the displacement field would be continuous), whereas the y -component of the electric field is continuous at the interface, because it is parallel to the sidewalls of the ridge.

Supplementary Figure S3

Figure S3. Transverse cross-section of the intensity distribution ($|\mathbf{E}(x,z)|^2$) at $y=12 \mu\text{m}$ from the cavity centre.

References

- [SI_1] Y. Augenstein, M. Roussey, T. Grosjean, E. Descrovi, and C. Rockstuhl, "Inverse design of cavities for Bloch Surface Waves interfaced to integrated waveguides," *Photonics and Nanostructures - Fundamentals and Applications* **52**, 101079 (2022).
- [SI_2] Y. Augenstein, A. Vetter, B. V. Lahijani, H. P. Herzig, C. Rockstuhl, and M.-S. Kim, "Inverse photonic design of functional elements that focus Bloch surface waves," *Light: Science & Applications* **7**, 104 (2018).